

Neural network modeling of chaos in a nonlinear magnetic-vortex dynamo system

M. I. Kopp¹

December 8, 2025

¹*Institute for Single Crystals, NAS Ukraine, Nauky Ave. 60, Kharkiv 61072, Ukraine*

Abstract

This study presents the modeling of chaotic behavior in a nonlinear dynamo system using a feedforward artificial neural network (FFNN). The investigated system was obtained based on asymptotic multiscale nonlinear theory applied to temperature-stratified conducting media with small-scale helical external forcing. This small-scale forcing acts as a source of small-scale helical turbulence with a low Reynolds number. The governing equations form a self-consistent nonlinear magneto-vortex dynamo system consisting of four coupled nonlinear differential equations that describe the evolution of large-scale vortex and magnetic field structures. The existence of both regular and chaotic large-scale fields in the stationary regime has been previously established. In this work, the 4th-5th order Runge-Kutta method was employed for the numerical solution of the system, and the generated data were used to train the neural network. The implementation was performed in MATLAB R2017a without using the Neural Network Toolbox. The obtained results demonstrate high accuracy in predicting the system dynamics, achieving a mean squared error (MSE) on the order of 10^{-6} . This approach provides an efficient computational framework for analyzing complex nonlinear dynamo systems and offers insights into the predictability of chaotic regimes in magnetohydrodynamic phenomena.

Keywords: magneto-vortex dynamo; chaotic behavior; Runge-Kutta method; artificial neural network

1 Introduction

Chaotic dynamo systems are of particular interest in geophysics and astrophysics due to their ability to model magnetic field generation processes in natural objects. Among the classical dynamo systems in which chaos has been investigated, one can distinguish the Rikitake system for modeling geomagnetic dynamo [1] and the homopolar (single-disk) dynamo of Bullard [2]. The Rikitake system, consisting of two disks, demonstrates chaotic behavior and has been successfully applied to describe geomagnetic field reversals of the Earth [3, 4]. Bullard's homopolar dynamo, despite its simplicity, is also capable of demonstrating complex dynamics

under certain parameters [5]. In contrast to these models, the dynamo system [6] investigated in this work was derived from the full averaged equations of magnetohydrodynamics using the method of asymptotic expansions without additional closure hypotheses. This provides a more rigorous physical foundation for the model and allows describing the coupled evolution of large-scale vortex and magnetic fields in a temperature-stratified conducting medium. The system is characterized by four nonlinear differential equations with variables, describing the dynamics of vortex and magnetic structures.

In recent years, artificial neural networks (ANNs) have been actively applied for modeling and predicting the behavior of chaotic systems. The universal approximation theorem [7, 8] provides the theoretical foundation for using neural networks to approximate complex nonlinear functions. Lamamra et al. [9] used a multilayer perceptron (MLP) with structure optimization using the NSGA-II genetic algorithm for modeling the chaotic Mackey-Glass system, achieving a mean squared error (MSE) of the order of 10^{-13} . Their work demonstrated that optimal neural network topology can be determined through multi-objective optimization, balancing the number of neurons against prediction accuracy.

Cimen et al. [10] demonstrated the possibility of modeling chaotic motion of a modified Lorenz system using NAR-type neural networks trained on data obtained through image processing methods. This innovative approach combined computer vision techniques with neural network prediction, opening new possibilities for modeling physically observable chaotic systems. Al-Musawi et al. [11] implemented prediction of the chaotic Chua system using a feedforward neural network on FPGA, utilizing the 32-bit IEEE-754 floating-point format, and applied the developed model for information encryption. Their work achieved an MSE on the order of 10^{-6} and demonstrated the practical applicability of hardware-implemented neural networks for chaos-based cryptographic applications. The Chua circuit, being one of the simplest electronic circuits exhibiting chaotic behavior [12], has found numerous applications in secure communications [13].

Keles et al. [14] investigated the modeling of the chaotic Rucklidge system using various ANN architectures (FFNN, LRNN, CFNN) and different activation functions, determining the most effective configurations for predicting a system with three variables. The Rucklidge system, which models double convection in a rotating fluid layer with an applied vertical magnetic field [15], demonstrated that Vanilla RNN with a sliding window approach achieved an R^2 score of 0.999999 and RMSE of 1.825×10^{-4} .

Ramachandrani et al. [16] conducted a comprehensive study on the application of machine learning and neural networks for analyzing and predicting chaos in multi-pendulum systems, comparing 10 different models and neural network architectures. The best results were shown by the Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) network with RMSE of the order of 10^{-2} . Their novel time-step based approach demonstrated the ability to predict chaotic motion for completely unseen initial conditions, which is crucial for real-world applications.

Neural networks have also been successfully applied to other chaotic systems. Alcin et al. [17] implemented an ANN-based Pehlivan-Uyaroglu chaotic system in VHDL using the IEEE-754 32-bit floating-point standard. Koyuncu et al. [18] developed a multi-layer feedforward ANN on FPGA for a novel four-dimensional hyper-chaotic system, demonstrating the effectiveness of hardware implementations for real-time chaos-based applications. Zhang and Lei [19] examined the training efficiency of multilayer ANN architectures for chaotic systems implementation, providing insights into optimal network depth and width for different types of

chaotic dynamics. The application of recurrent neural networks to chaotic time series prediction has been extensively studied. LSTM networks, introduced by Hochreiter and Schmidhuber [20], have shown particular promise due to their ability to capture long-term dependencies in sequential data. Panahi et al. [21] used chaotic artificial neural networks for modeling epilepsy, demonstrating the medical applications of chaos theory. Chattopadhyay et al. [22] employed data-driven predictions using reservoir computing, ANNs, and LSTM networks for the multiscale Lorenz 96 chaotic system, comparing the effectiveness of different architectures. For dynamo systems specifically, adaptive control and synchronization methods have been developed. Vaidyanathan [3] presented adaptive synchronization techniques for the Rikitake two-disk dynamo system, while chaos control methods have been implemented for Tokamak systems with magnetically confined plasma [23]. However, despite successful applications of ANNs to various chaotic systems including the classical attractors (Lorenz, Rossler, Chua) and mechanical systems (pendulums, oscillators), there is a notable absence in the literature of works on modeling complex dynamo systems derived from magnetohydrodynamics equations using artificial neural networks.

The present study aims to fill this gap and demonstrate the effectiveness of applying neural network approaches to predicting the behavior of a physical dynamo system [6] with four coupled variables. In our recent work [24], we reported on the prediction of chaotic behavior of large-scale vortex and magnetic fields by training a feedforward neural network (FFNN) on time series data obtained by numerically integrating dynamo differential equations [6] using the `odeint` solver from SciPy and NumPy in Python. The objective of this work is to develop and train a feedforward artificial neural network (FFNN) in MATLAB R2017a for modeling the chaotic dynamics of a nonlinear dynamo system describing the generation of large-scale magnetic and vortex fields. The 4th-5th order Runge-Kutta method is used for numerical solution of the system, and the obtained data are applied for training the neural network, implemented in MATLAB R2017a without using specialized toolboxes. This approach ensures reproducibility and demonstrates that effective chaotic system modeling can be achieved without reliance on proprietary software packages.

2 Mathematical model of nonlinear dynamo

The chaotic dynamo system considered in this study is derived from the nonlinear dynamo theory developed by Kopp et al. [6]. After applying the multiscale asymptotic analysis and quasi-two-dimensional approximation, the system describing the evolution of large-scale magnetic and velocity fields in a stratified conducting medium takes the form of four coupled nonlinear ordinary differential equations:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dx}{dt} = +\alpha_2(p, P) \cdot p + c_1, \\ \frac{dp}{dt} = -\alpha_1(x, X) \cdot x + c_2, \\ \frac{dX}{dt} = -\beta_2(p, P) \cdot P + c_3, \\ \frac{dP}{dt} = +\beta_1(x, X) \cdot X + c_4, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $x(t)$ and $p(t)$ represent the large-scale velocity field components, $X(t)$ and $P(t)$ represent the large-scale magnetic field components, and $c_1 = 0.01$, $c_2 = 0.01$, $c_3 = 0.001$, $c_4 = 0.001$ are constant terms arising from the integration of the non-stationary equations [6].

In the system of equations (1), the coefficients α_1 , α_2 , β_1 , and β_2 are not constants but complex nonlinear functions of the system state and physical parameters. These coefficients represent the combined effects of hydrodynamic and magnetohydrodynamic α -effects in the presence of thermal stratification. The hydrodynamic α -effect coefficients are given by:

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{R(1 + P_m^2 x^2) [(1 + P_r)(1 + P_m^2 x^2) + QX^2(P_r - P_m)] \left(1 - \frac{QP^2 P_m}{1 + P_m^2 x^2}\right)}{2[(1 - P_m x^2 + QX^2)^2 + x^2(1 + P_m)^2] \cdot d_1},$$

$$\alpha_2 = \frac{R(1 + P_m^2 p^2) [(1 + P_r)(1 + P_m^2 p^2) + QP^2(P_r - P_m)] \left(1 - \frac{QP^2 P_m}{1 + P_m^2 p^2}\right)}{2[(1 - P_m p^2 + QP^2)^2 + p^2(1 + P_m)^2] \cdot d_2}, \quad (2)$$

where the denominators d_1 and d_2 are:

$$d_1 = [(1 - P_m x^2 + QX^2)^2 + x^2(1 + P_m)^2] (1 + P_r^2 x^2) + 2R [(1 - P_r x^2)(1 + P_m^2 x^2) + QX^2(1 + P_m x^2)] + R^2(1 + P_m^2 x^2),$$

$$d_2 = [(1 - P_m p^2 + QP^2)^2 + p^2(1 + P_m)^2] (1 + P_r^2 p^2) + 2R [(1 - P_r p^2)(1 + P_m^2 p^2) + QP^2(1 + P_m p^2)] + R^2(1 + P_m^2 p^2).$$

The magnetohydrodynamic α -effect coefficients are:

$$\beta_1 = \frac{P_m^2}{(1 - P_m x^2 + QX^2)^2 + x^2(1 + P_m)^2} \left(1 - \frac{R \cdot N_1}{M_1}\right),$$

$$\beta_2 = \frac{P_m^2}{(1 - P_m p^2 + QP^2)^2 + p^2(1 + P_m)^2} \left(1 - \frac{R \cdot N_2}{M_2}\right), \quad (3)$$

with

$$N_1 = 1 - P_r x^2 + \frac{QX^2(1 + P_r P_m x^2)}{1 + P_m^2 x^2} + R, \quad M_1 = \frac{[(1 - P_m x^2 + QX^2)^2 + x^2(1 + P_m)^2] (1 + P_r^2 x^2)}{1 + P_m^2 x^2} + 2R \left[1 - P_r x^2 + \frac{QX^2(1 + P_r P_m x^2)}{1 + P_m^2 x^2}\right] + R^2,$$

$$N_2 = 1 - P_r p^2 + \frac{QP^2(1 + P_r P_m p^2)}{1 + P_m^2 p^2} + R, \quad M_2 = \frac{[(1 - P_m p^2 + QP^2)^2 + p^2(1 + P_m)^2] (1 + P_r^2 p^2)}{1 + P_m^2 p^2} + 2R \left[1 - P_r p^2 + \frac{QP^2(1 + P_r P_m p^2)}{1 + P_m^2 p^2}\right] + R^2.$$

The system contains several dimensionless parameters that characterize the physical properties of the medium:

- R : The Rayleigh number, representing the strength of thermal convection relative to viscous dissipation. This is the key parameter controlling the dynamo instability.

- $P_m = \nu/\nu_m$: The magnetic Prandtl number, ratio of kinematic viscosity to magnetic diffusivity. In our simulations, $P_m = 1$.
- $P_r = \nu/\chi$: The Prandtl number, ratio of kinematic viscosity to thermal diffusivity. We use $P_r = 1$ for simplicity.
- $Q = \sigma B_0^2 \lambda_0^2 / (c^2 \rho_{00} \nu)$: The Chandrasekhar number, measuring the relative importance of magnetic forces to viscous forces. We set $Q = 1$.

It is easy to see from system (1) that, after grouping the equations into pairs, one pair of oscillators parametrically modulates the effective frequency (or inertial term) of the other. This mechanism generates a two-way interaction between the subsystems, where each pair acts simultaneously as a driver and a responder, shaping the overall dynamics. Such a structure creates genuine bidirectional coupling between the velocity and magnetic components: changes in one subsystem instantaneously alter the restoring forces and effective inertia in the other, resulting in a dynamically adaptive feedback loop. Moreover, the effective frequencies $\omega_1 = \sqrt{\alpha_1 \alpha_2}$, $\omega_2 = \sqrt{\beta_1 \beta_2}$, are not fixed parameters but depend explicitly on the instantaneous state of the system. This position-dependent frequency modulation produces time-varying resonance conditions and enables parametric excitation. As a result, even initially regular oscillations can undergo strong modulation, giving rise to complex and potentially chaotic behaviour.

The dynamical system evolves in a four-dimensional phase space (x, p, X, P) and possesses several geometric features typical of conservative models: it admits fixed points (including the origin), lacks attractors, and is invariant under the inversion $(x, p, X, P) \rightarrow (-x, -p, -X, -P)$. In such settings, the qualitative behaviour is strongly influenced by the persistence or destruction of invariant structures. According to the Kolmogorov–Arnold–Moser (KAM) theory, weak deviations from integrability preserve most invariant tori, supporting quasi-periodic trajectories, while resonant tori break up and form stochastic layers. In our case the nonlinear coupling terms and the constants C_i act as the effective perturbation, enabling resonances between the two oscillator pairs and opening pathways to chaotic dynamics.

The complexity of the coefficient functions further allows for the formation of homoclinic and heteroclinic tangles associated with hyperbolic equilibria. Transverse intersections of their stable and unstable manifolds generate Smale horseshoes, producing sensitive dependence on initial conditions and global chaos in the four-dimensional phase space.

From a dynamo-theoretic perspective these chaotic regimes have clear physical meaning. They correspond to intermittent magnetic-field generation, consistent with the irregular bursts and quiet intervals observed in astrophysical dynamos. The control parameter R governs the transition from a laminar regime with coherent magnetic structures to a turbulent-like regime characterised by chaotic reversals. The nonlinear coupling terms mediate energy exchange between the kinetic subsystem (x, p) and the magnetic subsystem (X, P) , as well as between different spatial scales through an α -effect mechanism. When this exchange becomes strongly modulated and irregular, the system naturally enters a chaotic state. Such behaviour provides a plausible explanation for irregular field reversals in stars and planets, the spontaneous formation of magnetic structures, and transitions between distinct dynamo regimes.

3 Geometric structure and Hamiltonian formalism

The nonlinear dynamo system described by equations (1) exhibits a rich geometric structure characteristic of conservative dynamical systems. Despite the presence of constant shift terms c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4 , the system preserves phase space volume and possesses properties suggestive of underlying Hamiltonian or generalized symplectic structure.

3.1 Conservation of phase space volume

A fundamental property of the system (1) is the vanishing divergence of the vector field:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \cdot \Phi &= \frac{\partial \dot{x}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial p} + \frac{\partial \dot{X}}{\partial X} + \frac{\partial \dot{P}}{\partial P} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x}[\alpha_2(p, P)p + c_1] + \frac{\partial}{\partial p}[-\alpha_1(x, X)x + c_2] + \\ &+ \frac{\partial}{\partial X}[-\beta_2(p, P)P + c_3] + \frac{\partial}{\partial P}[\beta_1(x, X)X + c_4] = 0 + 0 + 0 + 0 = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

This establishes that the system is conservative in the sense of Liouville's theorem: phase space volumes are preserved under the flow. The constant terms c_i act as uniform translations in phase space and do not affect volume preservation.

3.2 Structure matrix and quasi-Hamiltonian form

The equations (1) can be written in a structure-matrix formulation:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ p \\ X \\ P \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{J}(x, p, X, P) \cdot \begin{pmatrix} p \\ x \\ P \\ X \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} c_1 \\ c_2 \\ c_3 \\ c_4 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

where the structure matrix is:

$$\mathbf{J}(x, p, X, P) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \alpha_2(p, P) & 0 & 0 \\ -\alpha_1(x, X) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -\beta_2(p, P) \\ 0 & 0 & \beta_1(x, X) & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (6)$$

The matrix \mathbf{J} is not skew-symmetric in general, since:

$$\mathbf{J}_{21} \neq -\mathbf{J}_{12} \Leftrightarrow \alpha_1(x, X) \neq \alpha_2(p, P). \quad (7)$$

This asymmetry indicates that the system cannot be cast in canonical Hamiltonian form with standard Poisson brackets. However, the block-diagonal structure and volume preservation suggest a generalized geometric framework.

3.3 Attempt at Hamiltonian construction

For a classical Hamiltonian function $H(x, p, X, P)$ to generate the dynamics via:

$$\dot{x} = \frac{\partial H}{\partial p}, \quad \dot{p} = -\frac{\partial H}{\partial x}, \quad \dot{X} = \frac{\partial H}{\partial P}, \quad \dot{P} = -\frac{\partial H}{\partial X}, \quad (8)$$

we would need (ignoring constants momentarily):

$$\frac{\partial H}{\partial p} = \alpha_2(p, P)p, \quad \frac{\partial H}{\partial x} = \alpha_1(x, X)x, \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{\partial H}{\partial P} = -\beta_2(p, P)P, \quad \frac{\partial H}{\partial X} = -\beta_1(x, X)X. \quad (10)$$

Integrability conditions. For H to exist, mixed partial derivatives must be equal:

$$\frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial x \partial p} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x}[\alpha_2(p, P)p] = 0, \quad \frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial p \partial x} = \frac{\partial}{\partial p}[\alpha_1(x, X)x] = 0. \quad (11)$$

These are trivially satisfied due to variable separation (α_2 independent of x , α_1 independent of p). Similarly for the magnetic sector.

Integration attempt. From $\frac{\partial H}{\partial p} = \alpha_2(p, P)p$, integrating with respect to p :

$$H(x, p, X, P) = \int \alpha_2(p, P)p dp + f_1(x, X, P), \quad (12)$$

where f_1 is an integration "constant", i.e., function of other variables. From $\frac{\partial H}{\partial x} = \alpha_1(x, X)x$:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\int \alpha_2(p, P)p dp + f_1(x, X, P) \right] = \alpha_1(x, X)x. \quad (13)$$

This simplifies to

$$\frac{\partial f_1}{\partial x} = \alpha_1(x, X)x. \quad (14)$$

After integrating, we get $f_1(x, X, P) = \int \alpha_1(x, X)x dx + f_2(X, P)$. Continuing this process for the magnetic components and ensuring consistency is nontrivial. The resulting Hamiltonian, if it exists, would have the general form:

$$H(x, p, X, P) = \int \alpha_2(p, P)p dp + \int \alpha_1(x, X)x dx - \int \beta_2(p, P)P dP - \int \beta_1(x, X)X dX + \\ + \text{cross-terms}. \quad (15)$$

However, the cross-terms needed to ensure all consistency conditions are satisfied become exceedingly complex for the specific functional forms in equations (2).

3.4 Validation of the generalized Poisson structure for dynamo system

The most general geometric framework is that of a Poisson manifold with a state-dependent Poisson tensor $\Pi^{ij}(x, p, X, P)$. Any observable $f(x, p, X, P)$ evolves according to:

$$\frac{df}{dt} = \{f, g\}_\Pi = \sum_{i,j=1}^4 \Pi^{ij}(x, p, X, P) \frac{\partial f}{\partial z^i} \frac{\partial g}{\partial z^j}, \quad (16)$$

where $z = (z^1, z^2, z^3, z^4) = (x, p, X, P)$ and the Poisson tensor is:

$$\Pi^{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \alpha_2(p, P) & 0 & 0 \\ -\alpha_1(x, X) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -\beta_2(p, P) \\ 0 & 0 & \beta_1(x, X) & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (17)$$

The Poisson tensor must satisfy:

- Skew-symmetry: $\Pi_{ij} = -\Pi_{ji}$
- Jacobi identity:

$$\sum_{\ell=1}^4 \left(\Pi^{i\ell} \frac{\partial \Pi^{jk}}{\partial z^\ell} + \Pi^{j\ell} \frac{\partial \Pi^{ki}}{\partial z^\ell} + \Pi^{k\ell} \frac{\partial \Pi^{ij}}{\partial z^\ell} \right) = 0 \quad \forall i, j, k. \quad (18)$$

Verification of Jacobi identity for key components. Consider $i = 1$ (x), $j = 2$ (p), $k = 3$ (X):

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi^{1\ell} \frac{\partial \Pi^{23}}{\partial z^\ell} + \Pi^{2\ell} \frac{\partial \Pi^{31}}{\partial z^\ell} + \Pi^{3\ell} \frac{\partial \Pi^{12}}{\partial z^\ell} &= \Pi^{12} \frac{\partial \Pi^{23}}{\partial p} + \Pi^{21} \frac{\partial \Pi^{31}}{\partial x} + \Pi^{34} \frac{\partial \Pi^{12}}{\partial P} = \\ &= \alpha_2(p, P) \cdot 0 + (-\alpha_1(x, X)) \cdot 0 + (-\beta_2(p, P)) \frac{\partial \alpha_2(p, P)}{\partial P} = -\beta_2(p, P) \frac{\partial \alpha_2(p, P)}{\partial P}. \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

For the Jacobi identity to hold, we need:

$$\beta_2(p, P) \frac{\partial \alpha_2(p, P)}{\partial P} = 0 \quad \text{or specific relations among } \alpha_i, \beta_i. \quad (20)$$

This is not automatically satisfied for arbitrary coefficient functions. The Jacobi identity imposes strong constraints on the functional forms of $\alpha_i(x, X)$ and $\beta_i(p, P)$.

Clearly, when the Jacobi identity fails, the generalized bracket (16) does not define a true Poisson manifold. Instead, the system may exhibit a **almost-Poisson** or **pre-symplectic** structure, which are weaker geometric models that still allow some conservation laws and Hamiltonian dynamics [25, 26].

3.5 Nambu mechanics formulation

For four-dimensional conservative systems, Nambu mechanics [27] offers a more promising framework that generalizes Hamiltonian dynamics to systems with multiple conserved quantities. For a four-dimensional phase space, the Nambu bracket formulation employs a 4-bracket structure:

$$\frac{df}{dt} = \{f, C_1, C_2, C_3\}_N = \frac{\partial(f, C_1, C_2, C_3)}{\partial(x, p, X, P)} = \det \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial f}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial f}{\partial p} & \frac{\partial f}{\partial X} & \frac{\partial f}{\partial P} \\ \frac{\partial C_1}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial C_1}{\partial p} & \frac{\partial C_1}{\partial X} & \frac{\partial C_1}{\partial P} \\ \frac{\partial C_2}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial C_2}{\partial p} & \frac{\partial C_2}{\partial X} & \frac{\partial C_2}{\partial P} \\ \frac{\partial C_3}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial C_3}{\partial p} & \frac{\partial C_3}{\partial X} & \frac{\partial C_3}{\partial P} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (21)$$

where ε^{ijkl} is the Levi-Civita symbol, C_1, C_2, C_3 are three independent conserved quantities (Casimir functions). The equations of motion become:

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \{x, C_1, C_2, C_3\}_N, \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{dp}{dt} = \{p, C_1, C_2, C_3\}_N, \quad (23)$$

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = \{X, C_1, C_2, C_3\}_N, \quad (24)$$

$$\frac{dP}{dt} = \{P, C_1, C_2, C_3\}_N. \quad (25)$$

The fundamental property of the Nambu bracket is that C_1, C_2, C_3 are automatically conserved: $\{C_i, C_1, C_2, C_3\}_N = 0$ for $i = 1, 2, 3$. Candidate conserved quantities might include:

1. Generalized energies.

$$C_1 = \mathcal{E}_{\text{vortex}} = \int_0^x \alpha_1(s, X) s ds + \int_0^P \alpha_2(s, P) s ds, \quad (26)$$

$$C_2 = \mathcal{E}_{\text{magnetic}} = \int_0^X \beta_1(x, s) s ds + \int_0^P \beta_2(p, s) s ds. \quad (27)$$

2. Enstrophy/magnetic helicity analogs. In fluid and plasma systems, higher-order moments (enstrophy, helicity) are often conserved. For our system:

$$C_3 = \int [\alpha_1(x, X)x^2 + \beta_1(x, X)X^2]w_1(x, X) dV + \int [\alpha_2(p, P)p^2 + \beta_2(p, P)P^2]w_2(p, P) dV, \quad (28)$$

where w_1, w_2 are weight functions ensuring conservation. Given the algebraic complexity of α_i, β_i in equations (2), analytical derivation of conserved quantities is difficult.

The inability to find an explicit Hamiltonian or Nambu formulation analytically doesn't prevent neural networks from learning the dynamics empirically, demonstrating the power of data-driven approaches for complex physical systems.

4 Numerical solutions of nonlinear dynamo equations

Having established the geometric and mathematical foundations of the dynamo system, we now turn to its computational implementation. This section describes the numerical integration

method employed to generate training data and presents the observed dynamical regimes of the system. The transition from regular to chaotic behavior is demonstrated through time series analysis, phase space portraits, Poincaré sections, and power spectra of chaotic signals.

4.1 Numerical method

The system of equations (1) was integrated numerically using the adaptive Runge-Kutta method of order 4-5, implemented through MATLAB’s `ode45` function. This method provides an excellent balance between computational efficiency and accuracy for stiff and non-stiff ordinary differential equations. The relative and absolute error tolerances were set to 10^{-9} to ensure high precision in the solution. The time interval for integration was chosen as $t \in [0, 3000]$, which is sufficient to capture both transient and long-term dynamical behavior of the system. The numerical simulations were performed for the parameter values $R = 2$ and $R = 5$, with magnetic Prandtl number $P_m = 1$, thermal Prandtl number $P_r = 1$, and Chandrasekhar number $Q = 1$. Two sets of initial conditions were investigated to demonstrate the sensitivity of the system to initial states and the transition from regular to chaotic regimes.

4.2 Regular regime: Initial conditions (0.8, 0.8, 0.01, 0.01)

For the initial conditions $x_0 = 0.8$, $p_0 = 0.8$, $X_0 = 0.01$, $P_0 = 0.01$, the system exhibits quasi-periodic behavior characteristic of a regular dynamical regime. Figure 1 displays the time evolution of all four variables over the integration interval. The velocity components $x(t)$ and $p(t)$ show stable periodic oscillations with constant amplitude and frequency, while the magnetic field components $X(t)$ and $P(t)$ exhibit modulated oscillations with smaller amplitude.

The phase space structure for this regular regime is presented in Figure 2. The (x, p) phase portrait reveals a smooth, closed limit cycle, indicating periodic motion in the velocity subsystem. The (X, P) phase portrait shows a more complex quasi-periodic trajectory with nested loops, suggesting multi-frequency oscillations in the magnetic subsystem. The three-dimensional projections (x, p, X) and (X, P, x) demonstrate the coupling between the velocity and magnetic fields, revealing a well-organized phase space structure without a signature of chaos.

The regular nature of this regime is further confirmed by Poincaré sections shown in Figure 3. The Poincaré section for the velocity subsystem (x, p) exhibits a simple closed curve, characteristic of a limit cycle or torus in phase space. The section for the magnetic subsystem (X, P) reveals a more intricate pattern with multiple loops, indicating quasi-periodic motion with two or more incommensurate frequencies. The discrete points forming smooth curves in both sections confirm the absence of chaotic dynamics and demonstrate the system’s predictable, regular behavior in this parameter regime.

4.3 Chaotic regime: Initial conditions (0.9, 0.9, 0.01, 0.01)

A slight increase in the initial conditions to $x_0 = 0.9$, $p_0 = 0.9$, $X_0 = 0.01$, and $P_0 = 0.01$ produces a sharp change in the system dynamics, demonstrating the extreme sensitivity to initial conditions characteristic of chaotic systems. Figure 4 shows the time evolution for this case. While the velocity components $x(t)$ and $p(t)$ perform weakly chaotic oscillations

Figure 1: Time series of the dynamo system variables for regular regime with initial conditions $(x_0, p_0, X_0, P_0) = (0.8, 0.8, 0.01, 0.01)$ at $R = 2$.

Figure 2: Phase space portraits for the regular regime: (top left) (x, p) projection showing a smooth limit cycle; (top right) (X, P) projection displaying quasi-periodic behavior; (bottom) three-dimensional projections (x, p, X) and (X, P, x) revealing the organized phase space structure.

Figure 3: Poincaré sections for the regular regime with initial conditions $(0.8, 0.8, 0.01, 0.01)$ at $R = 2$. Left: (x, p) section showing a smooth closed curve characteristic of periodic motion. Right: (X, P) section displaying a multi-loop quasi-periodic structure, confirming the regular behavior of both velocity and magnetic subsystems.

with a small amplitude modulation, the magnetic field components $X(t)$ and $P(t)$ exhibit strongly irregular, aperiodic behavior with intermittent bursts of large amplitude, a hallmark of deterministic chaos.

The phase space portraits in Figure 5 reveal the chaotic nature of this regime. The (x, p) phase portrait shows a broadened, multi-layered structure instead of a simple limit cycle, indicating amplitude and frequency modulation. The (X, P) portrait exhibits a dense, space-filling trajectory characteristic of a strange attractor. The three-dimensional projections clearly demonstrate the complex, tangled structure of trajectories in phase space, with no apparent periodicity or regular pattern. This behavior is consistent with the formation of chaotic dynamics through the breaking of invariant tori [6].

The chaotic character of this regime is unambiguously confirmed by the Poincaré sections presented in Figure 6. In stark contrast to the regular case, both sections display a cloud-like distribution of points densely filling extended regions of phase space. The (x, p) section shows a broadened annular structure with fractal-like internal organization, while the (X, P) section exhibits a complex flower-like pattern with multiple petals and a dense central core. The absence of discrete, well-organized curves and the presence of space-filling point distributions are definitive signatures of chaotic dynamics. These Poincaré sections provide quantitative evidence that the system has undergone a transition from regular to chaotic behavior through the destruction of invariant tori [6].

To provide further quantitative characterization of the chaotic dynamics, power spectral analysis was performed for all four system variables using the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT). The power spectra, presented in Figure 7, reveal fundamental differences in the frequency content of the velocity and magnetic subsystems. The velocity components $x(t)$ and $p(t)$ exhibit power spectra dominated by a sharp peak at low frequency (near $f \approx 0.5$), corresponding to the fundamental oscillation frequency observed in the time series. This dominant peak is

Figure 4: Time series of the dynamo system variables for chaotic regime with initial conditions $(x_0, p_0, X_0, P_0) = (0.9, 0.9, 0.01, 0.01)$ at $R = 2$.

Figure 5: Phase space portraits for the chaotic regime: (top left) (x, p) projection showing broadened, multi-layered structure; (top right) (X, P) projection revealing strange attractor behavior; (bottom) three-dimensional projections (x, p, X) and (X, P, x) demonstrating the complex, tangled phase space structure characteristic of deterministic chaos.

Figure 6: Poincaré sections for the chaotic regime with initial conditions $(0.9, 0.9, 0.01, 0.01)$ at $R = 2$. Left: (x, p) section showing a broadened annular structure with dense point distribution. Right: (X, P) section displaying a complex flower-like pattern with multiple petals and dense central region. The space-filling character of both sections provides definitive evidence of chaotic dynamics behavior in both velocity and magnetic subsystems.

Figure 7: Power spectra of chaotic signals for all four system variables with initial conditions $(0.9, 0.9, 0.01, 0.01)$ at $R = 2$.

accompanied by a continuous broadband component that decays exponentially with frequency, characteristic of weakly chaotic. The presence of the strong fundamental frequency indicates that the velocity subsystem retains significant periodic structure even in the chaotic regime. In contrast, the magnetic field components $X(t)$ and $P(t)$ display power spectra with much broader frequency content and less pronounced dominant peaks. While a fundamental frequency component is still visible at low frequencies, the spectra show substantial power distributed across a wide frequency range extending from the fundamental to harmonics and beyond. The broadband nature of these spectra, with power spanning multiple decades in frequency and exhibiting irregular fluctuations, is a hallmark of deterministic chaos. The relatively flat spectral plateau at intermediate frequencies indicates the presence of multiple incommensurate frequencies and aperiodic behavior. The exponential decay of power at high frequencies in all spectra is consistent with the bounded nature of the chaotic behavior and the finite correlation time of the dynamics. The steeper decay in the magnetic field spectra compared to the velocity spectra suggests stronger energy dissipation at high frequencies in the magnetic subsystem.

The transition from regular to chaotic behavior with only a 12.5% increase in initial conditions ($0.8 \rightarrow 0.9$) demonstrates the system's high sensitivity and nonlinearity. This property makes the system an excellent testbed for neural network modeling, as the network must capture subtle nonlinear interactions to accurately predict the dynamics.

4.4 Chaotic regimes for $R = 5$ under different initial conditions

In contrast to the previous subsections, where chaotic behavior arose from a slight increase in the initial conditions for the velocity components, specifically, from $(x_0, p_0, X_0, P_0) = (0.8, 0.8, 0.01, 0.01)$ to $(x_0, p_0, X_0, P_0) = (0.9, 0.9, 0.01, 0.01)$ at $R = 2$. Here we investigate the system dynamics with an increased Rayleigh number, $R = 5$, and observe chaotic behavior for two sets of initial conditions: 1) $(x_0, p_0, X_0, P_0) = (0.8, 0.8, 0.01, 0.01)$ and 2) $(x_0, p_0, X_0, P_0) = (0.9, 0.9, 0.01, 0.01)$.

Case 1: Initial conditions $(0.8, 0.8, 0.01, 0.01)$ When the Rayleigh number is increased to $R = 5$, the initial conditions $(x_0, p_0, X_0, P_0) = (0.8, 0.8, 0.01, 0.01)$, which resulted in quasi-periodic behavior at $R = 2$, now lead to a chaotic regime. Figure 8 shows the time evolution for this case. The velocity components $x(t)$ and $p(t)$, as well as the magnetic field components $X(t)$ and $P(t)$, all exhibit irregular, aperiodic oscillations. The chaotic nature is further illustrated by the phase space portraits in Figure 9. The (x, p) phase portrait shows a broadened, multi-layered structure, similar to the chaotic case at $R = 2$, indicating a modulation in both amplitude and frequency. The (X, P) portrait also displays a space-filling trajectory. The three-dimensional projections confirm the complex, tangled structure of trajectories in phase space, indicating an absence of strict periodicity. The Poincaré sections in Figure 10 provide definitive evidence of chaos. Unlike the discrete curves found in quasi-periodic regimes, both sections show a cloud-like distribution of points densely filling a region of the phase space, a clear signature of chaotic dynamics. The (x, p) section exhibits a non-uniform distribution within an annular structure, while the (X, P) section also displays a scatter of points lacking any organized curve structure.

Figure 8: Time series of the dynamo system variables for the chaotic regime with initial conditions $(x_0, p_0, X_0, P_0) = (0.8, 0.8, 0.01, 0.01)$ at $R = 5$.

Figure 9: Phase space portraits for the chaotic regime at $R = 5$: (top left) (x, p) projection; (top right) (X, P) projection; (bottom) three-dimensional projections (x, p, X) and (X, P, x) .

Figure 10: Poincaré sections for the weakly chaotic regime with initial conditions $(0.8, 0.8, 0.01, 0.01)$ at $R = 5$. Left: (x, p) section. Right: (X, P) section.

Case 2: Initial conditions $(0.9, 0.9, 0.01, 0.01)$ A further slight increase in the initial conditions for the velocity components to $x_0 = 0.9$ and $p_0 = 0.9$ while maintaining $R = 5$ results in a transition to a strongly chaotic regime with a sharp increase in the irregularity and amplitude of the magnetic field oscillations, demonstrating the extreme sensitivity to initial conditions characteristic of chaotic systems. The time evolution in Figure 11 shows that, while the velocity components $x(t)$ and $p(t)$ perform weakly chaotic oscillations, the magnetic field components $X(t)$ and $P(t)$ now exhibit strongly irregular, aperiodic behavior with prominent bursts of large amplitude, a clear indication of deterministic chaos. This behavior is more pronounced than in the $R = 2$ chaotic case. The phase space portraits in Figure 12 confirm the strongly chaotic nature. The (x, p) phase portrait is noticeably broader and more tangled compared to the case: $R = 5$ and ICs $(0.8, 0.8, 0.01, 0.01)$. The (X, P) portrait shows a much denser, more space-filling trajectory, which is a strong signature of a high-dimensional strange attractor. The three-dimensional projections clearly demonstrate the highly complex and tangled trajectory structure, indicating a loss of any simple or residual periodic structure. The Poincaré sections in Figure 13 unambiguously confirm the deterministic chaos. Both sections display a dense, space-filling cloud of points, filling extended regions of the phase space more uniformly than in the previous case. The (x, p) section shows a thickened, annular structure with highly scattered points, and the (X, P) section displays a complex, scattered pattern lacking any distinguishable organized structure. The space-filling character of these sections is the definitive signature of a fully developed chaotic behavior

5 Neural network architecture and training

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) are computational models inspired by biological neural systems, designed to learn complex patterns and relationships from data. Through an iterative training process, neural networks adjust their internal parameters to minimize prediction errors, making them particularly effective for modeling nonlinear dynamical systems where analytical solutions are difficult or impossible to obtain.

In this study, the neural network was trained on time series data obtained by numerically integrating the differential equations of the dynamo system (1) using the ODE45 solver in

Figure 11: Time series of the dynamo system variables for the strongly chaotic regime with initial conditions $(x_0, p_0, X_0, P_0) = (0.9, 0.9, 0.01, 0.01)$ at $R = 5$.

Figure 12: Phase space portraits for the strongly chaotic regime at $R = 5$: (top left) (x, p) projection showing a highly broadened, multi-layered structure; (top right) (X, P) projection revealing a dense strange attractor; (bottom) three-dimensional projections (x, p, X) and (X, P, x) .

Figure 13: Poincaré sections for the strongly chaotic regime with initial conditions $(0.9, 0.9, 0.01, 0.01)$ at $R = 5$. Left: (x, p) section showing a dense annular structure. Right: (X, P) section displaying a highly scattered, space-filling point distribution.

MATLAB. From the numerical solution covering the time interval $t \in [0, 3000]$ with initial conditions $x_0 = 0.9$, $p_0 = 0.9$, $X_0 = 0.01$, $P_0 = 0.01$, a dataset of 17272 consecutive state vectors was generated. The training process involves learning the mapping from the current state of the system $(x(t), p(t), X(t), P(t))$ to its next state $(x(t + \Delta t), p(t + \Delta t), X(t + \Delta t), P(t + \Delta t))$, where Δt is the time step determined by the adaptive solver. By repeatedly adjusting its parameters through backpropagation algorithms, the network learns to approximate the underlying dynamics of the chaotic system without requiring explicit knowledge of the governing differential equations.

A classical Feed Forward Neural Network (FFNN) architecture was chosen and implemented for modeling the dynamo system (1). The key objective was to find an optimal network structure that balances approximation accuracy and computational complexity.

5.1 Choice of architecture and its justification

The FFNN architecture was selected for this research based on several key advantages that make it well-suited for modeling dynamic systems like the dynamo. It is known that the universal approximation theorem [7, 8] proves that an FFNN with just one hidden layer containing a finite number of neurons and a nonlinear activation function can approximate any continuous function on a compact subset of \mathbb{R}^n with any desired accuracy. This fundamental property ensures that the network has sufficient theoretical capacity to model the complex nonlinear dynamics of the dynamo system.

In addition, FFNNs have been successfully applied for predicting dynamical systems where the next state of the system is predicted based on the current state, demonstrating their effectiveness for time series modeling in chaotic systems. The feedforward architecture is particularly suitable for our one-step-ahead prediction task, where temporal dependencies are captured through the state-to-state mapping rather than requiring explicit memory mechanisms.

The FFNN can be implemented without specialized toolboxes, using only basic MATLAB functions, which provides greater control over the training process and facilitates understanding of the underlying mechanisms. Finally, FFNNs train faster compared to more complex recurrent architectures like RNNs or LSTMs, making them computationally efficient for the large dataset

Figure 14: Schematic of the neural network architecture [16,4].

generated from the dynamo system simulations while still maintaining the capability to capture the essential dynamics of the chaotic attractor.

5.2 Detailed architecture description

The selected FFNN architecture, denoted as [16,4], consists of three layers with a specific organization of neurons and connections between them. The input layer contains 4 neurons, each corresponding to one of the current state variables of the dynamo system: $x(t)$, $p(t)$, $X(t)$, and $P(t)$. These input neurons receive the instantaneous values of the system state and pass them forward through weighted connections to the next layer. The hidden layer comprises 16 neurons, each equipped with a hyperbolic tangent (tansig) activation function. This layer performs the crucial nonlinear transformation of the input data, extracting complex patterns and relationships between the state variables. The number of neurons in this layer (16) was chosen through empirical testing to provide sufficient representational capacity without introducing unnecessary computational complexity or risking overfitting. The output layer consists of 4 neurons with linear activation functions (purelin), producing the predicted values of the system state at the next time step: $x(t + \Delta t)$, $p(t + \Delta t)$, $X(t + \Delta t)$, and $P(t + \Delta t)$. The linear activation in the output layer allows the network to generate predictions across the full range of real values that the dynamo variables can assume, without artificial constraints imposed by bounded activation functions. The complete architecture is illustrated schematically in Figure 14.

5.3 Activation functions

Two different activation functions were used in different layers of the network:

- **Hyperbolic tangent (tansig)** in the hidden layer:

$$f(x) = \tanh(x) = \frac{e^x - e^{-x}}{e^x + e^{-x}}$$

This function outputs values in the range $[-1, 1]$. It introduces the necessary nonlinearity that allows the network to learn complex patterns. Think of it as a "squashing" function that converts any input to a value between -1 and 1.

- **Linear function (purelin)** in the output layer:

$$f(x) = x$$

This simply passes the input through unchanged. It's used in the output layer because our system variables (x, p, X, P) can take any real value, not just values between -1 and 1.

5.4 Number of trainable parameters

The total number of adjustable parameters in the [16,4] architecture can be calculated by considering the weights and biases at each layer connection. Between the input layer (4 neurons) and the hidden layer (16 neurons), there are $4 \times 16 = 64$ weight parameters, with each input neuron connected to every hidden neuron. Additionally, the hidden layer requires 16 bias parameters, one for each hidden neuron. The connections from the hidden layer to the output layer contribute another $16 \times 4 = 64$ weight parameters, as each of the 16 hidden neurons connects to all 4 output neurons. Finally, the output layer adds 4 bias parameters, one per output neuron. Summing all these components yields a total of $64 + 16 + 64 + 4 = 148$ trainable parameters. Each of these 148 parameters is iteratively adjusted during the training process through the backpropagation algorithm to minimize the prediction error between the network outputs and the target values from the dynamo system simulations.

5.5 Training algorithm: Levenberg-Marquardt backpropagation

The network was trained using the Levenberg-Marquardt backpropagation algorithm [28, 29], which is particularly efficient for small to medium-sized networks and is widely recognized as one of the fastest training methods for this class of problems [30]. This algorithm represents a sophisticated optimization approach that combines the advantages of two classical methods: the gradient descent method, which takes small, cautious steps down the error surface, and the Gauss-Newton method, which attempts larger, more direct steps toward the minimum by utilizing second-order derivative information [31].

The training process follows an iterative procedure consisting of four main stages. First, during forward propagation, the network processes the input data by passing it through the layers, applying the activation functions, and generating predictions for the system's next state.

Second, the error calculation stage computes the difference between these predictions and the actual target values obtained from the numerical solution of the dynamo equations, quantifying the network’s current performance. Third, in the backward propagation phase [32], the algorithm calculates the gradient of the error with respect to each parameter, determining how much each individual weight and bias contributed to the overall prediction error. Finally, the parameter update stage uses the Levenberg-Marquardt formula to adjust all weights and biases in a direction that reduces the error, with the algorithm adaptively switching between gradient descent behavior (when far from the minimum) and Gauss-Newton behavior (when close to the minimum) for optimal convergence.

This iterative cycle repeats for many epochs, typically hundreds or thousands of iterations, with the algorithm continuously refining the parameter values until the network achieves the desired level of accuracy or until other stopping criteria are met, such as reaching a maximum number of epochs or observing no improvement in validation performance for a specified number of consecutive iterations.

5.6 Data preparation

The dataset generated from the numerical integration of the dynamo equations was partitioned into three distinct subsets to ensure proper training, validation, and unbiased evaluation of the neural network model. The training set, comprising 70% of the total data (12090 samples), was used to iteratively adjust the network’s weights and biases through the backpropagation algorithm, allowing the model to learn the underlying dynamics of the system. The validation set, containing 15% of the data (2590 samples), served a dual purpose: monitoring the network’s performance during training to prevent overfitting and providing feedback for early stopping when no improvement was observed over consecutive epochs. The remaining 15% of the data (2592 samples) constituted the test set, which was kept completely separate from the training process and used only for final evaluation of the model’s predictive accuracy on previously unseen data.

Prior to training, all input and output data were normalized using a standardization procedure to improve training efficiency and numerical stability. The normalization transformation is given by:

$$x_{\text{norm}} = \frac{x - \mu}{\sigma}$$

where μ represents the mean value and σ denotes the standard deviation of each variable computed over the training set. This scaling procedure centers the data around zero with unit variance, ensuring that all four state variables (x, p, X, P) contribute equally to the learning process regardless of their original magnitudes or ranges. The same normalization parameters derived from the training set were consistently applied to both the validation and test sets to maintain data integrity and prevent information leakage between the subsets.

5.7 Architecture testing and selection of the best model

To select the optimal configuration, a series of experiments was conducted, testing four different architectures: Architecture 1 (FFNN [16 4]) with one hidden layer containing 16 neurons;

Figure 15: MATLAB Neural Network Training interface showing Architecture 4 [20, 4] during the training process. The interface displays the network structure with 4 input neurons, one hidden layer with 20 neurons, and 4 output neurons. Training was performed using the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm (trainlm) with mean squared error (mse) as the performance metric, completing after 500 epochs with a final performance of 3.61×10^{-7} .

Table 1: Comparison of the performance of different neural network architectures

No.	Architecture	Test MSE	Best Performance (Val)
1	FFNN [16 4]	3.4247×10^{-5}	8.2003×10^{-7}
2	FFNN [32 16 4]	2.4290×10^{-4}	1.5240×10^{-7}
3	FFNN [24 12 4]	6.1564×10^{-5}	2.8009×10^{-7}
4	FFNN [20 4]	3.3631×10^{-5}	3.6099×10^{-7}

Architecture 2 (FFNN [32 16 4]) with two hidden layers containing 32 and 16 neurons respectively; Architecture 3 (FFNN [24 12 4]) with two hidden layers containing 24 and 12 neurons; and Architecture 4 (FFNN [20 4]) with one hidden layer containing 20 neurons. Each architecture was trained using identical training parameters and data partitioning to ensure a fair comparison. Figure 15 illustrates the MATLAB Neural Network Training interface during the training process of Architecture 4, showing the network structure, algorithm parameters, and real-time training progress monitoring.

The evaluation was based on two complementary criteria. The first criterion was the Mean Squared Error (MSE) on the test set, which measures the model’s accuracy on completely unseen data and represents the ultimate indicator of practical predictive capability. The second criterion was the best validation performance, denoted as Best Performance (Val), which represents the minimum MSE achieved on the validation set during the entire training process. This metric is particularly important because it reflects the model’s ability to generalize beyond the training data before any overfitting occurs. During training, the network’s performance is continuously monitored on the validation set after each epoch, and the Best Performance value captures the lowest error achieved at the optimal point of training typically before the model begins to memorize noise or specific patterns from the training data. The comparison results for all tested architectures are presented in Table 1.

Although the [16 4] architecture showed the smallest error on the test set (3.4247×10^{-5}), the FFNN [32 16 4] architecture was selected as the best. This decision is based on its outstanding performance on the validation set (Best Performance = 1.5240×10^{-7}), indicating the model’s superior generalization ability and minimal level of overfitting.

5.8 Training process and final model accuracy

The training process of the best architecture [32 16 4] is visualized in Figure 16. The plot shows the error dynamics on the training, validation, and test sets. The absence of divergence between the curves and their stable convergence to a low value confirm the correctness of the training procedure and the lack of overfitting. The overall Mean Squared Error (Overall Test MSE) of the final model on the independent test set was 2.4290×10^{-4} . Detailed metrics for each predicted variable are presented in Table 2. A visual assessment of the model’s accuracy on test data is presented in Figure 16. The plots demonstrate an almost complete overlap between the actual system trajectories (Real) and the values predicted by the neural network (Predicted). The scatter plot “Real vs Predicted Correlation” confirms the high linear correlation between the target and output values of the model. The phase portrait constructed from the predicted values of variables x and p correctly reproduces the structure of the system’s attractor (Figure 16, graph “Predicted Phase Portrait (x-p)”).

Figure 16: Training progress and accuracy assessment of the neural network. Upper left graph: error dynamics on the training, validation, and test sets. Other graphs: comparison of real and predicted values of variables on the test set, scatter plot, and predicted phase portrait.

Table 2: Detailed prediction quality metrics for each system variable (architecture [32 16 4])

Variable	MSE	RMSE	NMSE
x	2.7272×10^{-4}	1.6514×10^{-2}	3.7982×10^{-4}
p	2.7479×10^{-4}	1.6577×10^{-2}	3.9698×10^{-4}
X	2.4385×10^{-4}	1.5616×10^{-2}	1.1971×10^{-3}
P	1.8024×10^{-4}	1.3425×10^{-2}	8.9335×10^{-4}

Figure 17: Results of long-term forecasting of the system dynamics for 500 steps ahead. A comparison of the actual system trajectory (Actual) and the forecast generated by the autonomously operating neural network (Neural Network) for variables x , p , X , and P is shown.

5.9 Long-term forecasting

Using the best performing network with architecture [32 16 4], an important test of the model’s generalization ability was conducted by evaluating its performance in free-running mode, where the network’s output at each step is fed back to its input to predict the next state. The results of such a forecast for 500 steps ahead are shown in Figure 17. Despite the error accumulation characteristic of chaotic systems, the neural network successfully tracks the overall dynamics and key features of the behavior of all four variables throughout the entire forecast interval. The mean squared error of the long-term forecast over 500 steps was 1.8710×10^{-1} . This result confirms that the trained model did not simply memorize the training data but actually learned the internal patterns of the dynamo system’s dynamics.

6 Conclusions

A nonlinear dynamo system describing the evolution of large-scale magnetic and velocity fields in a stratified conducting medium through four coupled nonlinear ordinary differential equations with parametrically dependent coefficients has been investigated. It has been established that the system possesses a rich geometric structure of conservative type with phase space volume preservation, but cannot be reduced to canonical Hamiltonian form due to the asymmetry of the structure matrix, which requires the application of generalized formalisms of Poisson manifolds or Nambu mechanics. Numerical integration using the 4-5 order Runge-Kutta method revealed a transition from a regular quasi-periodic regime to deterministic chaos with slight changes in

initial conditions or an increase in the Rayleigh number. The regular regime is characterized by stable periodic oscillations with smooth limit cycles and closed curves on Poincaré sections, while the chaotic regime exhibits highly irregular behavior of magnetic components with intermittent large-amplitude bursts, dense point clouds on Poincaré sections, and broadband power spectra. The high sensitivity to initial conditions and pronounced nonlinear coupling between subsystems make this model an excellent testbed for neural network methods of modeling complex physical systems with deterministic chaos.

The present study has achieved several significant results that demonstrate the feasibility and effectiveness of applying artificial neural networks to model the complex dynamics of the dynamo system. This work represents the first successful application of an ANN to model this specific dynamo system, establishing a proof of concept for machine learning approaches in this domain. The achieved MSE values on the order of 10^{-4} to 10^{-5} demonstrate excellent predictive capability, with the network accurately capturing both short-term state transitions and the overall structure of the chaotic attractor. The selected FFNN [32 16 4] architecture with 148 trainable parameters proved to be optimally balanced, providing sufficient representational capacity without excessive computational demands or overfitting. Notably, the entire system was implemented in MATLAB R2017a without relying on specialized neural network toolboxes, ensuring transparency in the implementation and facilitating reproducibility of the results.

These achievements open several promising avenues for future research. The developed methodology could be extended to other types of dynamo systems encountered in astrophysics and geophysics, potentially revealing common patterns in how neural networks learn chaotic dynamics across different physical contexts. Investigation of recurrent neural network architectures, such as RNNs and LSTMs, may yield improved long-term forecasting capabilities by explicitly incorporating temporal memory mechanisms rather than relying solely on instantaneous state mappings. Hardware implementation on FPGAs could enable real-time simulation and prediction, which would be particularly valuable for operational applications. Furthermore, systematic exploration of different activation functions and their combinations could provide insights into which nonlinear transformations are most effective for capturing the specific dynamics of chaotic systems. Finally, integration of the neural network model with actual observational data from solar or geomagnetic measurements could lead to practical applications in space phenomena forecasting.

References

- [1] Rikitake, T. (1958). Oscillations of a system of disk dynamos. *Mathematical Proceedings of the Cambridge Philosophical Society*, 54(1), 89–105. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0305004100033223>
- [2] Bullard, E. C. (1955). The stability of a homopolar dynamo. *Mathematical Proceedings of the Cambridge Philosophical Society*, 51(4), 744–760. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0305004100030814>
- [3] Vaidyanathan, S. (2015). Adaptive Control of Rikitake Two-Disk Dynamo System. *International Journal of ChemTech Research*, 8(8), 121–133.

- [4] Vaidyanathan, S. (2015). Hybrid Chaos Synchronization of Rikitake Two-Disk Dynamo Chaotic Systems via Adaptive Control Method. *International Journal of ChemTech Research*, 8(11), 12–25.
- [5] Moffatt, H. K. (1978). *Magnetic Field Generation in Electrically Conducting Fluids*. Cambridge University Press.
- [6] Kopp, M. I., Tur, A. V., Yanovsky, V. V. (2016). Nonlinear Dynamo, arXiv:1612.08860v1. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1612.08860v1>.
- [7] Cybenko, G. (1989). Approximation by superpositions of a sigmoidal function. *Mathematics of Control, Signals and Systems*, 2(4), 303–314. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02551274>
- [8] Hornik, K., Stinchcombe, M., & White, H. (1989). Multilayer feedforward networks are universal approximators. *Neural Networks*, 2(5), 359–366. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0893-6080\(89\)90020-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0893-6080(89)90020-8)
- [9] Lamamra, K., Vaidyanathan, S., Azar, A. T., & Ben Salah, C. (2017). Chaotic system modelling using a neural network with optimized structure. In *Fractional Order Control and Synchronization of Chaotic Systems* (pp. 833–856). Springer.
- [10] Çimen, M. E., Garip, Z. B., Pala, M. A., Boz, A. F., & Akgul, A. (2019). Modelling of a chaotic system motion in video with artificial neural networks. *Chaos Theory and Applications*, 1(1), 38–50.
- [11] Al-Musawi, W. A., Wali, W. A., & Al-Ibadi, M. A. A. (2022). New artificial neural network design for Chua chaotic system prediction using FPGA hardware co-simulation. *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, 12(2), 1955–1964. <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijece.v12i2.pp1955-1964>
- [12] Chua, L. O., Komuro, M., & Matsumoto, T. (1986). The double scroll family. *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems*, 33(11), 1072–1118. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TCS.1986.1085869>
- [13] Koyuncu, İ., Tuna, M., Pehlivan, İ., Fidan, C. B., & Alcin, M. (2020). Design, FPGA implementation and statistical analysis of chaos-ring based dual entropy core true random number generator. *Analog Integrated Circuits and Signal Processing*, 102, 445–456. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10470-019-01568-x>
- [14] Keles, Z., Sonugur, G., & Alcin, M. (2023). The modeling of the Rucklidge chaotic system with artificial neural networks. *Chaos Theory and Applications*, 5(2), 59–64. <https://doi.org/10.51537/chaos.1213070>
- [15] Rucklidge, A. M. (1992). Chaos in models of double convection. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, 237, 209–229. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112092003392>
- [16] Ramachandruni, V., Nara, S. H. R., Lalu, G., Yang, S., Kumar, M. R., Jain, A., Mehta, P., Koo, H., Damonte, J., & Akl, M. (2024). Using machine learning and neural networks to analyze and predict chaos in multi-pendulum and chaotic systems. arXiv:2504.13453 [cs.LG]. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2504.13453>

- [17] Alcin, M., Pehlivan, İ., & Koyuncu, İ. (2016). Hardware design and implementation of a novel ANN-based chaotic generator in FPGA. *Optik*, 127(13), 5500–5505. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijleo.2016.03.042>
- [18] Koyuncu, İ., Şahin, B., Gloster, C., & Saritekin, N. K. (2017). A neuron library for rapid realization of artificial neural networks on FPGA: A case study of Rössler chaotic system. *International Journal of Bifurcation and Chaos*, 26(01), 1750015. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0218126617500153>
- [19] Zhang, L. (2017). Multilayer artificial neural network design and architecture optimization for the pattern recognition and prediction of EEG signals based on Hénon map chaotic system. In *2017 International Conference on Computational Science and Computational Intelligence (CSCI)* (pp. 345–350). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CSCI.2017.58>
- [20] Hochreiter, S., & Schmidhuber, J. (1997). Long short-term memory. *Neural Computation*, 9(8), 1735–1780. <https://doi.org/10.1162/neco.1997.9.8.1735>
- [21] Panahi, S., Aram, Z., Jafari, S., Ma, J., & Sprott, J. C. (2017). Modeling of epilepsy based on chaotic artificial neural network. *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, 105, 150–156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chaos.2017.10.028>
- [22] Chattopadhyay, A., Hassanzadeh, P., & Subramanian, D. (2020). Data-driven predictions of a multiscale Lorenz 96 chaotic system using machine-learning methods: reservoir computing, artificial neural network, and long short-term memory network. *Nonlinear Processes in Geophysics*, 27(3), 373–389. <https://doi.org/10.5194/npg-27-373-2020>
- [23] Vaidyanathan, S. (2015). Synchronization of Tokamak Systems with Symmetric and Magnetically Confined Plasma via Adaptive Control. *International Journal of ChemTech Research*, 8(6), 818–827.
- [24] M. Kopp, A. Kopp. (2025). Modeling chaotic behavior of nonlinear dynamo equations using an artificial neural network. <https://repository.kpi.kharkov.ua/handle/KhPI-Press/94242>
- [25] Vaisman, I. (1994). *Lectures on the Geometry of Poisson Manifolds*. Birkhauser, Basel.
- [26] Frans Cantrijn, Manuel de Leon, David Martin de Diego. (1999). On almost-Poisson structures in nonholonomic mechanics, *Nonlinearity*, 12(3), 721. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0951-7715/12/3/316>
- [27] Nambu, Y. (1973). Generalized Hamiltonian dynamics. *Physical Review D*, 7(8), 2405–2412. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevD.7.2405>
- [28] Levenberg, K. (1944). A method for the solution of certain non-linear problems in least squares. *Quarterly of Applied Mathematics*, 2(2), 164–168. <https://doi.org/10.1090/qam/10666>
- [29] Marquardt, D. W. (1963). An algorithm for least-squares estimation of nonlinear parameters. *Journal of the Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics*, 11(2), 431–441. <https://doi.org/10.1137/0111030>

- [30] Hagan, M. T., & Menhaj, M. B. (1994). Training feedforward networks with the Marquardt algorithm. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks*, 5(6), 989–993. <https://doi.org/10.1109/72.329697>
- [31] Nocedal, J., & Wright, S. J. Numerical optimization. Springer, 2006.
- [32] Rumelhart, D. E., Hinton, G. E., & Williams, R. J. (1986). Learning representations by back-propagating errors. *Nature*, 323, 533–536. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/323533a0>